

Early adoption of Free and Open Source Software in a Higher School of Education:

students' views in the academic and future professional contexts

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Overview of presentation

- portuguese context
- our school context
- the study
- results
 - participants: software usage
 - arguments for choosing software
- final thoughts

Portugal - Viseu

- minimum wage = 400€
- Windows Vista Home Basic = 219€
- Windows Office 2007 Basic (student) = 160€

Polytechnic Institute of Viseu: Higher School of Education

- oldest higher school of education
- one of the biggest polytechnic
- undergraduate and postgraduate programs in Teacher Ed., Plastic Arts and Multimedia, Media Studies, Cultural Animation, Social Education, Sports and Physical Activity and Environmental Ed.
- 1200 students and 75 teachers
- every program: at least one ICT course
- six computer labs = classrooms
+ one student lab

FOSS landmarks - 2008

- 2005 – Moodle server for HSEV
- 2006 – Polytechnic buys WebCT
- 2008 – HSEV refuses shifting to WebCT
- ✓ Moodle as official e-learning platform for HSEV
- ✓ ICT courses that mainly use FOSS: Blender, Open Office, Kompozer, Gimp, Cinelerra, Audacity, Gcompris, ...
- ✓ FOSS, CC and Open Access as learning topics in some courses (residual)
- ✓ Final projects using FOSS (Arts and Teach. Ed.)

FOSS landmarks - 2008

Teachers and students involved in the debate about usage of FOSS in HSEV:

- spread ideas behind the potential of FOSS
- bring students and teachers to a dimension of debate where software choices aren't based only in:
 - economic cost
 - software features
 - marketing strategies
 - brand awareness
 - ...
- raise important ethical issues:
 - software choice as a statement about the world we live in and how we choose to live in it**